

Research Paper

Comparative performance analysis of eutectic salt-water solutions in latent thermal energy storage for residential applications: Insights from the ECHO project[☆]

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the potential of eutectic salt-water solutions as phase change materials (PCMs) for Cooling Thermal Energy Storage (CTES) systems, with a focus on residential applications under the Horizon Europe ECHO project. The research addresses the pressing need for sustainable, compact, and efficient thermal energy storage systems to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and improve energy efficiency in alignment with EU climate objectives. Among the evaluated PCMs, a Na₂CO₃/H₂O eutectic solution, enhanced with graphite, demonstrated considerable performance, achieving a 78 % increase in thermal conductivity in the liquid phase and a 55 % improvement in the solid phase compared to the base solution, while maintaining a strong latent heat of melting (284 kJ/kg) and low subcooling (1.97 K). Comprehensive experimental methods, including Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and Transient Plane Source (TPS) analysis, were employed to characterize the thermophysical properties of the PCMs. These techniques ensured precise measurements of latent heat, specific heat capacity, and thermal conductivity, with uncertainties of ± 2 % and ± 5 % for DSC and TPS measurements, respectively. Comparative analysis of the custom-made Na₂CO₃/H₂O solution with graphite and two commercial PCMs highlighted the advantages of the custom formulation, particularly in terms of reactivity and thermal conductivity, making it a strong candidate for CTES integration.

This work provides significant contributions to the understanding of eutectics thermophysical properties, a critical yet underexplored area, and sets the stage for the practical implementation of advanced LTES systems. The findings emphasize the importance of precise experimental characterization for accurate modeling and system optimization, laying the foundation for future efforts in scaling and deploying full-scale CTES units for energy-efficient residential applications.

1. Introduction

Effectively addressing climate change requires targeted interventions in sectors that significantly contribute to the global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions profile. Notably, the building sector is a major emitter, accounting for 26 % of total GHG emissions and 30 % of

global energy consumption [1]. These numbers highlight the urgent necessity for innovative and effective solutions aimed at reducing the carbon footprint of buildings. The urgency is further underscored by the European Union's ambitious climate objectives, as outlined in the Fit-for-55 package and the REPowerEU plan [2,3]. These initiatives seek to drastically reduce GHG emissions, foster a rapid transition to clean

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energy sources, and decarbonize the energy sector, with the long-term goal of achieving climate neutrality by 2050.

In the search for solutions to enhance the energy efficiency of buildings and maximize the use of renewable energy, thermal energy storage (TES) emerges as a promising technology. TES has the capacity to bridge fluctuations in energy demand within buildings, enabling the decoupling of energy supply and energy demand on the grid. This mismatch is one of the most critical challenges associated with renewable energy sources. Despite TES not being a recent technology, it has recently garnered increased attention within the scientific community, owing to its numerous benefits, such as increased compactness, greater operational flexibility, improved indoor air quality, and reductions in pollutant and GHG emissions [4]. According to a study conducted by Arce et al. [5], which analysed the impact of a realistic penetration rate of TES in the industrial and building sectors, the implementation of TES could result in a reduction of up to 7.5 % in carbon dioxide equivalent emissions and a 7.5 % decrease in final energy consumption in the European context.

Among TES technologies, Latent Thermal Energy Storage (LTES) systems, which utilize phase change materials (PCMs), are identified as the most promising solution [6]. LTES systems are particularly notable for their high energy density and their ability to store thermal energy within narrow temperature ranges, providing an effective mechanism to balance the disparity between energy supply and demand. The operational principle of LTES is based on the phase transition of PCMs, which allows for the absorption or release of substantial amounts of latent heat, thereby significantly improving thermal energy storage efficiency [7,8]. The energy storage density of PCMs is three to four times greater than that of materials that utilize sensible heat transfer [9]. This feature is particularly valuable for the integration of intermittent renewable energy sources, enhancing energy efficiency and reducing dependence on fossil fuels. Moreover, thanks to this characteristic, LTES systems are more cost-effective than sensible heat storage systems (STES), requiring smaller volumes and less weight for equivalent energy storage capacity [10]. This reduced space requirement, especially when compared to traditional water tanks, is particularly relevant for residential applications, where compactness is a primary requirement, especially in urban environments.

However, although LTES represents a mature technology, its potential remains constrained by the high costs associated with installation and maintenance. These costs are a direct result of the limited availability of full-scale installations employing these systems. These challenges are even more pronounced in cooling thermal energy systems (CTES), where LTES systems are currently more prevalent for high-temperature applications compared to low-temperature uses, such as refrigeration and air conditioning. This disparity is likely due to the higher installation costs of low-temperature integrated systems, which are themselves linked to the complexity of application-specific system designs, as well as the lack of full-scale measurement equipment for performance monitoring [11]. However, given the increase in global average temperatures, cold storage solutions offer significant potential for shifting peak electrical loads in buildings.

A primary distinction in CTES systems can be made between passive and active solutions. Passive systems incorporate PCMs directly into the building envelope, such as windows, walls, roofs, and floors. In contrast, active systems include technologies such as air conditioning (AC) systems, ice storage, evaporative cooling, and radiative cooling. Faraj et al. [12] performed an extensive review of the state-of-the-art CTES systems for buildings and emphasized that the difficulties commonly associated with LTES are even more significant for active CTES. The optimization of active CTES systems requires a combination of simulations, numerical analyses, and experimental investigations to enable their implementation, control, and evaluation [12].

Selvnes et al. [13] conducted a comprehensive review of recent advances in CTES research, focusing on applications employing commercial PCMs within the temperature range down to -65°C . Their analysis

categorized applications into areas such as commercial and residential refrigeration, food transport and packaging, and air conditioning. Yang et al. [14] similarly reviewed CTES research for sub-zero temperature applications, ranging from 0°C to -270°C , highlighting that while the number of simulations and experimental studies focusing on sub-zero CTES using PCMs is rapidly increasing, research remains limited and primarily concentrates on plate-shaped and slurry-based configurations.

Al-Abidi et al. [11] investigated CTES for air conditioning, identifying promising methods for enhancing heat transfer within thermal energy storage systems employing PCMs. Masood et al. [15] reviewed the state-of-the-art CTES implementation in the built environment, focusing on overcoming the low thermal conductivity characteristic of PCMs. They emphasized that increasing the heat transfer area of LTES devices should not be the sole approach for improving energy storage efficiency. Instead, a combination of strategies, such as adding nanoparticles, PCM encapsulation, fins, and metallic foams, should be applied to optimize PCM performance more effectively. A growing body of experimental research has also examined the use of PCM-enhanced tanks as alternatives to conventional water tanks. For instance, Allouche et al. [16] compared the performance of a 100 L CTES tank equipped with a four-tube bundle heat exchanger against a conventional water tank for air conditioning, reporting a 26 % increase in indoor comfort duration and a 53 % improvement in storage capacity employing the commercial PCM RT15. Kabeel et al. [17] tested four PCMs (paraffin wax, stearic acid, capric-palmitic acid, and $\text{CaCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and observed average energy savings compared to conventional water tanks of 76 %, 78 %, 72 %, and 65 %, respectively. Fang et al. [18] evaluated an ice-storage system incorporating a helical heat pipe, achieving a coefficient of performance (COP) between 2.1 and 2.3. Similarly, Jia et al. [19] developed a cylindrical tank with helical finned aluminum tubes and used paraffin composited with expanded graphite, achieving a COP improvement of 7–10 %. Moreno et al. [20] reported a 36 % increase in storage capacity using S10 salt hydrate in a CTES tank with a 4.2 kW cooling system. Borri et al. [21] conducted both experimental and numerical characterizations of a cylindrical container, analyzing the thermal profiles of three sub-zero PCMs (aqueous calcium chloride, aqueous ethylene glycol, and decane). They underscored the importance of correctly characterizing PCM behavior through experimental investigations, particularly addressing subcooling effects, which are often inadequately considered in numerical modeling.

Overall, more experimental studies are necessary to comprehensively evaluate the potential of CTES for residential applications. While component-level numerical analyses offer detailed insights, simplifications at the system level often result in overestimated energy savings. The absence of experimental data further complicates the validation of numerical models, particularly when estimating economic impacts, which depend on location-specific factors such as energy costs, available incentives, and technology penetration rates. A comprehensive metric system is required to truthfully assess the effects of TES applications in buildings [22]. The need for real-world studies comparing different scenarios, and particularly for systems employing sub-zero PCMs, remains critical [14].

1.1. CTES within the HORIZON-EU project ECHO

In this context, the HORIZON-EU Project ECHO (Efficient Compact Modular Thermal Energy Storage System, Project No. 101096368) aims to develop a sustainable, modular, and digitally controlled thermal energy storage (TES) solution [23]. The project focuses on designing and demonstrating novel modular, compact, high-performance, and plug-and-play TES systems capable of providing heating, cooling, and hot water production. The system is intended to store energy for building applications for a period of at least four weeks. A particular emphasis is placed on integrating thermochemical materials (TCMs) with phase change materials (PCMs) to create a TES system capable of efficiently addressing the demands of space heating and hot water production.

The ECHO project is designed to be adaptable to different climatic, energy policy, and user requirement scenarios across Europe, with test sites planned in Italy, Belgium and Serbia. The system will be engineered for versatility, allowing it to integrate into building heating systems, operate within a smart electricity grid, or function in buildings not connected to district heating and cooling networks. Key performance metrics include storage efficiency, durability, cost reduction, and environmental impacts assessed through life cycle analysis (LCA) and life cycle cost analysis (LCCA). In regions with a predominant cooling demand, the project incorporates a cooling thermal energy storage (CTES) system specifically designed for air conditioning, featuring sub-zero melting point PCMs. According to the project's objectives, the CTES system will have the capability to store energy equivalent to at least 3 kW of cooling power for three hours.

The CTES system will be integrated into the secondary refrigeration circuit of a dedicated heat pump (HP) based on a PCM/single-phase fluid design. This heat pump will serve both the heating and cooling sections of the ECHO system, enabling operation at temperatures below the phase change point of the CTES PCM during charging. During discharging, the PCM in the CTES system will absorb heat from the water circuit connected to the end-user system, thereby delivering the required cooling power (Fig. 1). The selected heat pump will operate at -6°C with an inlet flow rate of 1100 l/h and a power output of 5 kW at the evaporator during the CTES charging mode. Combining all the results from the experimental measurements described in the following with results from Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations carried out on a scaled prototype, the final configuration of the cold ice accumulator will be made by a tank of roughly 300 l full of a mixture water/ethylene glycol blend (0.7/0.3 wt) coming from the HP, with eutectics PCMs encapsulated in 18 HDPE tubes (Tube ice© from PCM products) (Fig. 2).

The selection of PCMs for the ECHO CTES system involves careful consideration of factors such as melting temperature, compatibility with other system materials, chemical stability, and thermophysical properties [6]. However, the behavior of PCMs, particularly at sub-zero temperatures, still presents considerable gaps in terms of experimental characterization. The present study focuses on the selection process for low-melting-point PCMs, supported by a comprehensive experimental campaign to assess their thermophysical properties. The study outlines

Fig. 2. Final configuration of the cold accumulator.

the systematic steps involved in selecting PCMs, providing a detailed rationale for each choice. The results of the experimental measurements include critical properties such as phase change temperature, heat

Fig. 1. Schematic of the CTES within the ECHO TES design.

capacity, latent heat, and thermal conductivity. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was used to determine the heat capacity and latent heat of melting and solidification of four eutectic solutions. Additionally, two methods—DSC and a self-designed experimental procedure—were employed to evaluate the phase change temperature of the samples. The thermal conductivity of the materials was measured using a Transient Plane Source (TPS) method with a Hot Disk apparatus.

Based on these experimental analyses, $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{graphite}$ was identified as the most suitable PCM for the ECHO CTES system. This selection will inform further research aimed at determining the optimal configuration for integrating the PCM into the cold accumulator. This work represents a significant step toward developing efficient and sustainable cooling solutions that align with the objectives of Project ECHO.

2. Materials

Water, one of the most well-known and historically significant PCMs, has been utilized for cold thermal energy storage for over 2,000 years. Today, the use of ice (natural ice and snow) remains the state-of-the-art method for CTES applications. This prevalence is primarily due to the cost-effectiveness of such solutions, the favorable thermophysical properties of water, and its long-term chemical stability [24].

However, water is not a suitable PCM for applications requiring a phase change temperature range slightly above or below 0°C . Selecting a PCM for a CTES system—or for any LTES application in general—is challenging due to the numerous parameters that must be considered, including [25]:

- A phase change temperature consistent with the application;
- High thermal capacity;
- Favorable heat exchange properties, i.e. high thermal conductivity;
- High energy density;
- Minimal volumetric changes during melting/solidification;
- Low or negligible subcooling;
- Long-term chemical stability;
- Compatibility with other materials;
- Safety criteria, such as non-flammability and non-toxicity.

From an economic and environmental perspective, it is also critical that PCMs are abundant, commercially available, cost-effective, and

preferably recyclable to minimize their lifecycle impact.

Currently, no PCM fulfills all these criteria simultaneously. A key limitation of all PCMs is their generally low thermal conductivity [26]. Despite their high energy density, the slow solidification and melting times resulting from low thermal conductivity limit their practical application.

PCMs can be classified in various ways, one of which is based on their chemical nature [10]. They are generally categorized into:

Organic materials (e.g., paraffins, fatty acids, fatty alcohols, and polymers)

Inorganic materials (e.g., hydrated salts and metals)

Eutectic materials, which can be organic-organic, inorganic-inorganic, or organic-inorganic mixtures.

Many reviews are available today classifying PCMs for LTES applications, discussing their advantages, disadvantages, and methods to enhance their efficiency [926]. A schematic representation of PCMs as a function of their melting temperature and latent heat of melting presented in Fig. 3.

Organic materials are chemically and thermally stable, non-corrosive, recyclable, and exhibit high latent heat of melting. However, they are typically flammable, possess low phase change enthalpy and thermal conductivity, and often exhibit poor compatibility with encapsulation materials. Moreover, largely employed PCMs such as paraffins suffer from significant volume expansion during phase change [10].

Inorganic materials, on the other hand, are generally cost-effective and exhibit faster phase transitions due to their higher thermal conductivity. Nevertheless, they are often corrosive, prone to significant subcooling and phase segregation, and may have limited thermal stability. These factors make inorganic PCMs more suitable for industrial applications, such as high-temperature heat recovery [10]. To mitigate phase segregation and subcooling, nucleating agents are frequently incorporated into eutectics.

Organic PCMs, on the other hand, exhibit self-nucleation properties, minimizing subcooling and enabling phase transitions that closely align with theoretical predictions.

Finally, eutectic mixtures consist of two or more components that solidify simultaneously at a specific freezing point—the eutectic temperature. This temperature represents the lowest melting point

Fig. 3. PCMs as a function of latent heat of melting and melting temperature [9].

achievable by the mixture. Upon solidification, the mixture forms a solid containing two or more distinct phases while maintaining the overall composition of the liquid. As such, density differences between the phases do not result in settling. Eutectic PCMs exhibit sharp melting temperatures and favorable storage densities. For instance, organic–inorganic eutectics can combine the benefits of both material types, offering a potential solution for a wide range of applications [27]. Inorganic–inorganic eutectics, such as salt-based systems, provide improved stability and more controlled phase change temperatures compared to single-salt systems.

In CTES applications, PCMs are typically paraffins or eutectic compounds. Due to challenges such as chemical and thermal stability and corrosion, organic PCMs are still preferred to inorganic ones for large-scale applications despite their higher costs, although for sub-zero temperature applications, eutectic water-salt solutions are widely employed PCMs. Indeed, to address limitations associated with single PCMs, eutectics—comprising mixtures of organic and/or inorganic materials—have garnered increasing interest.

In their study Selvnes et al. [13] provide a comprehensive summary on commercially available PCMs with phase change temperatures between $-65\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, compiling an extensive list of market options. Similarly, Li et al. [28] reviewed PCMs operating between $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Organic PCMs, such as paraffins, and eutectics can generally achieve operational ranges as low as $-60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, while some commercial eutectics reach $-114\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ [13].

Overcoming the challenges of subcooling and phase segregation in eutectics would enhance their thermal conductivity and storage capacity, making them the preferred choice for CTES systems. Yang et al. [14] reviewed water-salt eutectic solutions for CTES applications, highlighting advancements in research on nano-additives and composite PCMs for sub-zero temperatures. These materials incorporate nanoparticles or porous matrices to enhance performance. Additionally, multicomponent eutectic mixtures can be tailored to achieve specific phase change temperatures, making them highly practical. However, achieving this requires a deeper understanding of thermophysical properties derived from experimental measurements, which remain limited for eutectics [27].

2.1. Materials selection within the ECHO project

In this regard, the ECHO project specifically focuses on eutectic water-salt solutions possessing melting temperatures below $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, giving particular attention to the experimental assessment of the thermophysical properties of the samples studied.

The target phase change temperature for the ECHO project's cold accumulator storage system is between 0 and $-6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Based on this target phase change temperature, additional selection criteria for the development of the inorganic salt-water eutectic system were established as follows:

- (i) the inorganic salt should be easily obtainable and cost-effective;
- (ii) the eutectic system should possess a melting enthalpy above 200 kJ/kg ;
- (iii) the eutectic system should display a single, sharp melting behaviour in differential scanning calorimetry (DSC);
- (iv) the melting properties should remain stable after successive DSC analyses.
- (v) Finally, since the goal of ECHO is to develop a sustainable TES solution that is widely accessible and adaptable to various socio-economic scenarios (different countries, architectural contexts, TES policies, and levels of consumer acceptance of these technologies), the cost-effectiveness of the technology—starting with the cost of the PCM—emerges as a fundamental criterion.

A literature search was conducted to identify potential inorganic salt candidates that might exhibit a eutectic point within the desired

temperature range [28,29]. Following this, the research focused on determining the eutectic point and the thermophysical properties of the eutectic solutions. The study identified MgSO_4 and Na_2CO_3 as promising, low-cost candidates for a eutectic system.

To select the most suitable PCM for Project ECHO, a detailed analysis of the thermal properties of the two base eutectic mixtures, $\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, was conducted using DSC at the Chemical Engineering Department of Istanbul Technical University. A TA Instruments Q2000 differential scanning calorimeter was utilized to measure the eutectic solution samples, calibrated using indium. A more extended explanation on the DSC methodology is given in Section 2.1. The analyses were conducted under an inert atmosphere of 50 mL nitrogen. The temperature program followed for the test included an initial isothermal step, followed by a non-isothermal ramp in which the temperature of the chamber was increased linearly at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Additionally, TiO_2 was employed as a nucleating agent to eliminate any phase separation or subcooling issues during freezing, and it was used in very small amounts (not exceeding $0.1\text{ wt}\%$) to prevent any distortion in the DSC analysis when determining the phase change characteristics of the inorganic salt-water systems.

In determination of the eutectic composition by using the DSC instrument, the eutectic and the solid–liquid transition peaks have been observed to determine the eutectic point. For determination of the eutectic composition, varying salt concentrations have been studied. More specifically, in the concentration region where promising data were collected, detailed concentration adjustments have been conducted with smaller $\text{wt}\%$ increments. Finally, the eutectic compositions and the phase change properties in distilled water have been determined successfully for the binary system. Both of the binary systems exhibit solely the eutectic phase peak without any secondary solid–liquid transition peak.

For $\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the eutectic composition was found to be $35.7\text{ wt}\%$ in water (equivalent to $17.4\text{ wt}\%$ MgSO_4), and for Na_2CO_3 , it was $5.75\text{ wt}\%$ in water.

The $\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system showed a melting onset at $-5.81\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, a peak at $-3.87\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and a melting enthalpy of 227.0 kJ/kg , surpassing the 200 kJ/kg threshold. Similarly, the $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system exhibited a melting onset at $-3.16\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, a peak at $-1.92\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and a higher melting enthalpy of 308.6 kJ/kg . Both systems melted in a single step with sharp peaks, making them suitable for the ECHO project. However, due to its higher latent heat value—about 36% greater—within the desired temperature range, the $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system was prioritized for further development in the project. Moreover, the $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system has melting onset and peak temperatures closer to the working temperature of the ECHO TES system, which will provide better melting/freezing cycles of the eutectic system and more efficient utilization of its latent heat capacity for cold storage. Furthermore, the required amount of salt (Na_2CO_3 and $\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in water is around 83% lower in the $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which is an advantage for eutectic solution preparation for the ECHO TES system, further reducing the production cost of the PCM. Further details on this stage of research and in-depth analysis of these findings will be provided in a dedicated paper. For these multiple reasons—namely, higher solidification temperature, greater latent heat, and lower salt requirement for solution production—the $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ eutectic was considered the preferred option, and all subsequent investigative efforts were therefore focused on this solution.

To enhance the thermal conductivity of the mixture—typically one of the primary limitations of PCMs—the $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution was modified by adding graphite at the Institute of Condensed Matter Chemistry and Energy Technologies of National Research Council (ICMATE-CNR).

For the fabrication of $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{graphite}$ composite, 0.005 g of the surfactant Triton X100 (Sigma-Aldrich) were dissolved into 94.15 g of deionised water (Millipore, Billerica MA, USA, $18.2\text{ M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$). After surfactant dissolution, 5.75 g of Na_2CO_3 (Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 99.5\%$) were added to the solution and dissolved at room temperature.

Afterwards, 10 g of graphite powder (Thermo Scientific, APS 7–11 μm , 99 %) were added under vigorous stirring and then ultra-sonicated using a Sonics VCX-130 tip-sonicator operated at 90 W and 20 kHz for 15 min.

According to the theoretical density of graphite, which is 2.2 g/cm^3 and that the density of the Na_2CO_3 solution is 1.05 g/cm^3 , a volume fraction of 4.5 vol% on the final volume of the sample can be calculated.

To broaden the range of options, the choice was made to compare the properties of the selected materials with commercially available PCMs that followed the same criteria applied to the custom-made solutions. This selection process resulted in a selection of four salt-based PCMs for the ECHO project's cold accumulator: two custom-made formulations, CM1 and CM2, and two commercially available products (by PCM Products), Plus ice© E-2 and E-3, chosen based on their phase change temperatures and latent heat.

Following this, a further phase of experimentation focused on the thermophysical properties of these solutions.

The final compositions of the selected PCMs are presented in Table 1. Since the two products from PCM Products, E-2 and E-3, are protected by commercial secrecy, it is not possible at this stage to provide further details beyond what has already been disclosed by the manufacturer, including specifics regarding their composition.

Once this selection of four materials was finalized, the thermo-physical properties of the samples were characterized.

3. Methods

3.1. Specific heat capacity and latent heat

The heats of melting and solidification, as well as the specific heat capacity of the samples, were measured at the Construction Technologies Institute of the National Research Council of Italy (ITC-CNR) using a DSC methodology.

3.1.1. Apparatus

The apparatus employed for the measurements is a MicroCalvet differential scanning calorimeter. A simplified schematic of the setup is shown in Fig. 4. While a detailed description of the DSC technique can be found in the literature [30–33], only the key aspects of the methodology are described here. This technique allows for the measurement of temperature and heat flow rates associated with changes in the state of the sample as a function of time and temperature. From these data, it is possible to derive the heat capacity and enthalpies of materials within the temperature range of -45 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for this specific apparatus.

In the apparatus, two pans—one containing the sample and the other serving as a reference—are positioned within a high thermal conductivity metal cylinder, which is enclosed in two aluminum housings, one internal and one external. The temperature of these housings is controlled by a dual-stage regulation system using Peltier-effect thermoelements. The analyses were carried out under an inert nitrogen atmosphere.

The temperature program for the test began with an initial isothermal step of 300–1000 s (depending on the sample) to stabilize the samples, followed by a non-isothermal ramp in which the chamber temperature was linearly increased at a rate of 0.1–1.2 K/min. Subsequently, a new isothermal step was performed at the final temperature for a specified duration. During this process, heat was transferred to both pans, and the acquisition system recorded the temperature, as measured by platinum resistance thermometers, along with the differential heat

flow between the sample and reference pans. From the heat flow curves as a function of time, the isobaric heat capacity of the sample at a given temperature T can be calculated using the following equation:

$$c_{p,m}(T) = k(T) \frac{M}{m \cdot \beta} \Delta\phi(T) \quad (1)$$

where m and M represent the mass and molar mass of the sample, β is the heating rate, $\Delta\phi$ is the differential heat flow rate between the sample and reference pans at the given temperature T , and k is a temperature-dependent factor that accounts for the difference between the thermal capacity of the calibrant material according to the literature and the experimentally measured value.

For the heat capacity measurements, the manufacturer declared an instrument uncertainty of 2 %. However, prior to initiating the experiments, a preliminary test was conducted to measure the heat capacity of water as a reference fluid over a wide temperature range from 0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The test was performed with a scanning rate of 0.2 K/min. The measured values were then compared with reference data from Refprop 10.0 [34], which reports a declared uncertainty of 0.1 % for liquid water. As depicted in Fig. 5, where the yellow area represents the 2 % error margin, a systematic positive deviation was assessed between experimental and reference data, consistently falling within the 2 % range but for a few values at temperatures exceeding 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Consequently, the manufacturer's declared accuracy was considered reliable.

Regarding the enthalpy of melting, the manufacturer provided a measurement certificate for a test performed on a 3.88 mg sample of naphthalene as the reference fluid. The certified value and declared uncertainty were 18.923 kJ/mol and 0.083 kJ/mol, respectively. To further verify the instrument's accuracy, an additional test was conducted at the ITC-CNR facility in Padua using a 3.88 mg sample of naphthalene. The results, graphically represented in Fig. 6, revealed a deviation of 0.023 kJ/mol between the measured and standard values, thereby confirming the instrument's accuracy.

3.2. Phase change temperature

Although differential scanning calorimetry is a well-established method for determining heat of melting, specific heat, and melting point in latent-heat storage applications [19], it shares a limitation with Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA) in that it tests only small sample sizes. This limitation can lead to discrepancies when compared to bulk materials used in practical applications, particularly regarding the degree of subcooling [35]. For this reason, a simpler method was employed at ITC-CNR to assess the freezing temperatures of the mixtures.

The method involved filling two 45 ml test tubes with the PCM under consideration and a reference material (ethanol), both initially maintained at ambient temperatures above the PCM's freezing point. These test tubes were then placed vertically inside a freezer. Temperatures were simultaneously measured for the tested fluid, the reference ethanol, and the surrounding air using a platinum thermal resistance sensor placed in the middle of the test tubes, with an accuracy of 0.05 K.

Furthermore, to evaluate the solidification rates of the considered PCMs, additional tests were conducted at the Institute of Condensed Matter Chemistry and Energy Technologies of CNR, on CM1, CM2, E-2, and E-3 to compare their solidification behaviours. A sample of each PCM was immersed in a thermostatic water/glycol (70/30 wt%) bath. The PCM sample was contained within a polyethylene cylinder with a diameter of 23 mm and a height of 70 mm (sample volume 28 cm^3), with a wall thickness of 1 mm, and tested in a vertical position. The temperature profile of the sample was measured using a K-type thermocouple placed at the centre of the sample.

Initially, the temperature of the sample was stabilized at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in an appropriate thermostatic bath. The temperature stability in the bath was ± 1 mK, and the expanded uncertainty ($k = 1$) was determined to be ± 0.02 K. Once thermal equilibrium was achieved, the sample was

Table 1

Chemical composition of the selected PCMs.

PCM	Composition
CM1	$\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (5.75/94.25 wt%)
CM2	$\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{graphite}$ (5.17/84.83/10 wt%)
E-2	n.d.
E-3	n.d.

Fig. 4. Schematic of the DSC apparatus (on the left) and the sample pan mechanism (on the right).

Fig. 5. Results from the DSC test with water as the reference fluid. Curve: experimental data from this study, Dots: data from Refprop 10.0 [34].

immersed in a “cold” thermostatic bath equilibrated at $-12\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the temperature of the sample was monitored until a new thermal equilibrium was reached.

3.3. Thermal conductivity

At ITC-CNR, the thermal conductivity of the four samples was measured at ambient pressure, within the temperature range of 243 K to 303 K.

3.3.1. Apparatus

A hot disk instrument, model TPS2500S, employing the transient plane source method (TPS), was used to measure thermal conductivity of samples. The core of the apparatus is the TPS sensor, displayed in Fig. 7. This sensor consists of a double spiral of thin nickel wire, Kapton-insulated, clamped between two blocks of the sample container in order to ensure its proper connection with the solution to be measured.

The operation is as follows: the TPS sensor functions both as a heat

source and a temperature sensor. Heat is generated by applying an electric current impulse, which raises the temperature of the sensor. The increase in temperature within the sensor is then measured by its electrical resistance:

$$R(t) = R_0[1 + \alpha\Delta T(t)] \quad (2)$$

where R_0 is the resistance of the TPS sensor under steady-state conditions, α is its temperature coefficient of resistance, and $\Delta T(t)$ is the time-dependent temperature increase.

The sample quantity is selected to prevent thermal waves from reaching the boundaries, ensuring the sample behaves as an infinite medium and avoids edge effects.

To ensure accurate measurements, the initial part of the data is excluded to eliminate the influence of insulation, the sensor’s heat capacity, and potential air bubbles. The excluded portion is determined based on discrepancies between the observed and theoretical temperature increases over time.

The power supplied during each measurement ranged from 75 mW

Fig. 6. Results from the DSC test with naphthalene as reference fluid.

Fig. 7. Schematic of the TPS sensor (on the left) and the sample container (on the right).

to 105 mW, with a power input duration of 3 s. The declared instrument accuracy is 5 %. To verify this value, preliminary tests were conducted using water as a reference fluid, yielding a maximum average deviation (MAD) of 4.6 %. Specifically, 38 measurements were performed for water across a temperature range of 288 K to 318 K, with power input durations of 2 s, 3 s, and 4 s. The experimental results were subsequently compared to data from Refprop 10.0 [34,36], which reports an uncertainty of 1.5 % for liquid water within this temperature range. The calculated average absolute deviation (AAD) relative to Refprop was 1.58 %, with the optimal power input time of 3 s achieving an AAD of 1 %. Fig. 8 presents the results from the water reference test.

4. Results

4.1. Specific heat capacity and latent heat

A high thermal capacity and a phase change temperature consistent with the intended application are fundamental criteria in the selection of

a phase change material (PCM). Fig. 9 illustrates the behaviour of the specific heat capacity for the samples. As shown, the addition of graphite in CM2 significantly reduces the specific heat absorbed, as graphite does not participate in the phase change. While the specific heat capacities of CM1 and CM2 are nearly identical in the solid phase, in the liquid phase, the specific heat capacity of CM2 is reduced by 7 % compared to CM1, thereby decreasing its thermal inertia.

The measured data were then correlated using a second-degree polynomial, as expressed in Eq. (3):

$$c_p = aT^2 + bT + c \text{ Eq. (3)}$$

where the coefficients a , b , and c for the solid and liquid phases of the four PCMs are listed in Table 2. The absolute average deviation (AAD) between the measured values and those calculated using the relationship in Eq. (1) was found to be 0.1 %, 0.4 %, 0.1 %, and 0.2 % for CM1, CM2, E-2, and E-3, respectively.

Table 3 presents the enthalpies of melting and solidification for the four PCMs.

Due to the aforementioned issues associated with the small sample size analyzed using the DSC technique, the latent heat of solidification reported in Table 3 is inconsistently lower than that of melting. Therefore, in the subsequent analysis, the latent heat of melting has also been considered as an index for the solidification process.

4.2. Phase change temperature

The resulting temperature curves for the four PCMs are presented in Fig. 10. Table 4 shows the melting temperatures and the degree of subcooling observed for each fluid. These quantities were calculated based on the work of Zhang et al. [37] through the analysis of the first derivative of the measured temperature with respect to acquisition time. This analysis allows for the identification of the start and end of the phase change process, corresponding to the two main peaks in the temperature's first derivative trend. Consequently, the melting temperature reported in Table 4 is calculated as the average temperature measured between the start and end of the phase change.

As shown in Fig. 11, CM2 begins its solidification approximately 12 min earlier than CM1, which may lead to an increased fraction of the PCM solidifying within the accumulator. This, in turn, could enhance the

Fig. 8. Percentage deviation between measured thermal conductivity of water and reference data from Refprop 10.0 [34] (representing the baseline).

Fig. 9. Heat capacity behavior of PCM samples.

Table 2
Coefficients from Eq.3.

	CM1			-	CM2			-	E-2			-	E-3		
	a	b	c		a	b	c		a	b	c		a	b	c
solid	-0.07	5.99	1818		0.50	23.07	1919		0.25	21.25	2292		0.64	33.55	2174
liquid	-0.01	0.81	3688		-0.02	1.55	3616		0.00	-0.19	3990		0.01	-1.05	3801

amount of cooling energy absorbed through latent heat exchange during the three operating hours prescribed by the project.

Subcooling represents one of the major limitations of eutectics and

inorganic PCMs. This phenomenon occurs when the temperature of the PCM during solidification drops below its phase change temperature, creating an undesirable effect that complicates PCM applications. This

Table 3

Enthalpies of melting and solidification for the PCMs measured using the MicroCalvet apparatus.

PCM	Phase Change Temperature	Latent heat of melting	Latent heat of solidification
	[°C]	[kJ/kg]	[kJ/kg]
CM1	-2.1	317.7	289.0
CM2	-2.1	284.0	260.0
E-2	-2.1	323.2	288.4
E-3	-3.0	332.8	290.2

challenge is particularly significant in CTES systems, which are typically designed to operate within narrow temperature ranges. As highlighted in Table 4, all the analyzed samples exhibit subcooling below 2 K. Notably, the addition of graphite to CM2 increases its subcooling by 0.5 K compared to CM1, while the commercial PCM E-3 demonstrates the lowest subcooling, measuring only 0.88 K.

4.3. Thermal conductivity

Accurately determining the thermal conductivity of a PCM is crucial for assessing its heat transfer performance. This knowledge is fundamental for the optimal design of heat exchangers, ensuring the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the test system. Thermal conductivity data, measured for the four samples according to Section 2.3, are reported in Table 5, whereas Fig. 12 presents the thermal conductivity of the samples in comparison to that of pure water. It is evident that the thermal conductivities of CM1, E-2, and E-3 are nearly identical. In contrast, the thermal conductivity of CM2, in which the salt-water solution is mixed with micrometric graphite particles, is significantly higher—approximately 78 % higher in the liquid phase and 55 % higher in the solid phase compared to CM1. This substantial increase illustrates the significant improvement achieved through the addition of graphite particles.

The measured data were then correlated using linear fitting, as depicted in Eq.2:

$$\lambda = aT + b \text{ Eq. (4)}$$

Where the coefficients a and b for the solid and liquid phases for the four PCMs are reported in Table 6. An average absolute deviation (AAD) of 0.5 %, 1.8 %, 0.3 %, and 1 % was observed between the measured values and those calculated using the relationship in Eq. 4 for CM1,

CM2, E-2, and E-3, respectively.

5. Discussion

The analysis of the CTES system revealed that the two materials, CM2 and E-3, demonstrate significant potential, each offering distinct advantages and limitations. The addition of graphite as a in CM2 markedly improves its thermal conductivity, achieving an increase of up to + 1.06 W/mK in liquid phase compared to E-3 at the same temperature. However, this enhancement comes at the cost of a reduced latent heat of melting and a higher degree of subcooling, as the graphite does not participate in the phase change. Despite this, the subcooling observed across all four PCMs tested was relatively minimal. Consequently, future research should focus not mainly on subcooling mitigation but rather on accurately representing its behavior in thermal exchange modeling and simulations.

The selection of a PCM must carefully consider the thermophysical properties in relation to the intended application. For the ECHO project, which requires a CTES system capable of storing 9 kWh over a span of three hours, material reactivity emerges as a critical criterion. CM2 demonstrates significantly higher reactivity compared to E-3 and other analyzed samples, as illustrated in Fig. 11. This characteristic compensates for its lower thermal capacity by enhancing the efficiency of latent heat exchange within the required timeframe, thereby increasing the amount of heat stored. Furthermore, the slightly higher phase change temperature of CM2, though still below zero as mandated by the application, initiates the phase transition earlier than other PCMs, reducing the storage volume required for the targeted 9 kWh. This reduction is particularly beneficial in urban residential applications where space is a limiting factor.

Economic considerations also play a pivotal role. Even though E-3 is a commercially available product with an optimized production process,

Table 4

Main characteristics of the selected PCMs.

PCM	Melting Temperature [°C]	Subcooling [°C]
CM1	-2.1	-1.44
CM2	-2.1	-1.97
E-2	-2.1	-1.21
E-3	-3.0	-0.88

Fig. 10. Temperatures variation during solidification for CM1, CM2, E-2, and E-3 PCMs.

Fig. 11. Solidification rate for CM1, CM2, E-2 and E-3 (a).

Table 5

Measured thermal conductivities for the four eutectics from Table 1.

CM1		CM2	
T (K)	λ (W/m K)	T (K)	λ (W/m K)
303.35	0.620	303.35	1.042
293.35	0.594	293.35	1.070
288.35	0.588	288.35	1.079
283.35	0.585	283.35	1.085
278.25	0.582	278.4	1.031
273.55	0.569	273.25	0.985
268.55	0.563	268.1	3.102
266.55	1.969	263.2	3.193
263.65	2.018	258.25	3.237
258.75	2.087	253.25	3.268
253.85	2.116	243.95	3.386
244.05	2.196		
E-2		E-3	
T (K)	λ (W/m K)	T (K)	λ (W/m K)
303.35	0.602	303.35	0.621
293.35	0.601	293.35	0.589
288.35	0.598	288.35	0.578
283.35	0.597	283.35	0.574
278.35	0.590	278.35	0.569
263.55	2.106	263.55	2.131
258.65	2.172	258.65	2.209
253.65	2.217	253.65	2.155
243.85	2.320	243.85	2.253

CM2, though not yet widely produced, is composed of well-known and conventional materials. This composition suggests potential for cost-effective large-scale production in the future. Additionally, CM2's custom-made nature and known composition open possibilities for further enhancements, such as incorporating metallic foam instead of graphite to boost thermal exchange properties or adding thickening agents to mitigate subcooling effects.

Subsequently, the integration of PCM within LTES systems must also account for the design of the storage configuration itself. Modeling proves invaluable in this context, enabling engineers to predict thermal performance and optimize system parameters prior to implementation. Analytical models provide straightforward and rapid insights but are limited by idealized assumptions, making them less suited for complex scenarios. In contrast, numerical models, particularly computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations, excel in addressing the intricacies of

LTES systems, such as variable material properties and multi-dimensional heat transfer dynamics. Consequently, within the ECHO project, a CFD model of a scaled cold accumulator – based on the geometry shown in Fig. 2 – was developed to optimize parameters and guide the preliminary design phase using Ansys/Fluent software.

To validate this model, a scaled prototype will be built at ITC-CNR in Padua. Following validation, more extensive analyses of various configurations will be conducted. Ultimately, based on the results of prototype testing and simulations, a full-scale storage unit will be constructed and integrated into the ECHO system for evaluation in different case studies. This comprehensive approach ensures that the selected PCM and system design are both technically and economically viable, paving the way for effective implementation in real-world applications.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Latent Thermal Energy Storage (LTES) systems hold huge potential as a transformative solution for enhancing energy efficiency and reducing the carbon footprint of residential buildings. With their high energy density, compact design, and operational flexibility, LTES systems address critical energy challenges while supporting the transition toward cleaner energy sources. However, despite their advantages, widespread adoption remains limited by the need for advanced material development and system integration.

In this context the ECHO project, aimed at developing a modular and cost-effective TES system, exemplifies this effort by focusing on both heating and cooling applications. In particular, the project targets a sub-zero Cooling Thermal Energy Storage (CTES) system that integrate phase change materials. This system is designed to store energy for up to three hours, with a minimum capacity of 9 kWh, to balance energy demand in residential settings.

A key aspect of this initiative is the selection and evaluation of eutectic PCMs for CTES. The present study identified two potential eutectic salt-water solutions, ultimately prioritizing $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ based on its superior thermal properties. This eutectic exhibited a high latent heat of melting at 308.6 kJ/kg and a melting point of -1.92°C , which aligned closely with the operational requirements of the CTES system. To further enhance its performance, graphite was added to improve thermal conductivity, resulting in a 78 % increase in the liquid phase and a 55 % improvement in the solid phase. These enhancements

Fig. 12. Thermal conductivity of PCM samples compared to pure water.

Table 6
Coefficients from Eq.4.

	CM1		-	CM2		-	E-2		-	E-3	
	a	b		a	b		a	b		a	b
solid	-0.0097	1.9236		-0.011	3.0629		-0.0107	2.0098		-0.005	2.094
liquid	0.0015	0.5691		-0.0022	1.1107		0.0002	0.5949		0.002	0.553

significantly improved the reactivity and thermal exchange efficiency of the PCM while maintaining low subcooling characteristics.

Thermophysical properties are crucial for accurately modeling and optimizing LTES systems, yet the behavior of eutectics is still underexplored. This study addresses this gap by providing detailed experimental data on properties such as thermal conductivity, specific heat capacity, and phase change behavior, which were analyzed through experimental methods such as Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and the Transient Plane Source (TPS) technique. The modified $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ eutectic was compared against commercial PCMs, E-2 and E-3, revealing that while E-3 demonstrated the highest latent heat (332.8 kJ/kg) and the lowest subcooling (0.88 K), the custom solution with graphite offered superior conductivity and reactivity, initiating phase change earlier and reducing the required storage volume.

This work represents a significant contribution to the field by not only advancing the understanding of thermophysical properties but also integrating these insights into the development of innovative LTES systems.

Looking forward, the next phase of the project involves validating these findings through scaled prototype testing and advanced numerical simulations. The ultimate goal is to build and deploy full-scale CTES units, ensuring their technical and economic feasibility for widespread residential adoption.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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